

Person with a weapon test - Psychometric Properties

Study of Validity and Reliability in a research sample of two thousand cases in the Argentine Population

Research Project:

Research work on the Person with a weapon test. Psychometric Properties. Study of Validity and Reliability in a research sample of Two Thousand Cases in the Argentine Population.

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- Training in Non-Verbal Communication and Deception Detection - **METT- SETT (Microexpressions Training Tool & Subtle Expressions 3.0)**, Dr. Paul Ekman | <https://www.paulekman.com>
- **W.C.C.B.T.** World Confederation of Cognitive and Behavioral Therapies | <https://wccbt.org>

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VÁLIDO PARA SU USO EN ÁREA CLÍNICA, LABORAL Y FORENSE

TEST DE PERSONA CON ARMA

TOMO I

PROPIEDADES
PSICOMÉTRICAS

BAREMO ARGENTINO Y ESTUDIO
DE VALIDEZ Y CONFIABILIDAD
EN MUESTRA DE DOS MIL CASOS

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Prologue

Psychologists dedicated to the study of psychological assessment form a network in which we interweave our interests, findings, and doubts. This community enthusiastically embraces every new scientific production, every initiative, every result, every novelty, because it enriches our conceptual base and promotes increasing rigor in our field of work in the face of the many questions we receive from various domains, both within and outside our discipline.

Characterized in this way, as an interconnected network of thinking minds, our knowledge is never entirely our own; instead, it is constructed from what others have thought and experienced.

The Person with a weapon test is a good example of this.

Since its creation by Luis Morocho Vázquez (2002), which emerged from an adaptation of the Human Figure Drawing (HFD) test initially proposed by Florence L. Goodenough, through its implementation in our country starting in 2008 with police populations (Ministry of Security of the province of Mendoza), and later reflected in the publication of Marta Díaz de Dragotta's book *Applications of the Person with a weapon test* (2015), we now arrive at this new book by Irene Sirianni, which takes a further step by presenting the psychometric properties of the test based on a sufficiently large research sample.

Works like the one presented in this volume, which constitutes the first part of the author's exhaustive task, represent a value that not only benefits the validity and reliability of the technique for those who administer it but also adds the value of providing new support for the scientific foundations of using projective techniques in general and graphic techniques in particular.

Qualitative assessment, often underestimated in the face of the "shine" of quantification, finds in the present text the opportunity to position itself at a level of rigor that justifies its trust. The integration of the quantitative and qualitative, from a methodological perspective, is an ideal to which we aspire, though we do not always succeed. This is the merit of the author in her data systematization work!

The Person with a weapon test, as a projective technique rooted in all the knowledge gained from drawing the human figure, presents great utility in the workplace when investigating sensitive variables related to prevention and safety in specific environments.

The inclusion of the weapon in the prompt given to the person being evaluated, as is the case in the "Person in the Rain" test, constitutes a quality that triggers effects that can be analyzed beyond the person's drawing itself.

This thus opens a valuable interpretive universe for indirectly investigating the subject's unconscious world, while also allowing insight into the social representations and values of a specific community.

However, it is the systematic work with a valid methodology, consistent with the theoretical frameworks, that makes its scientific use possible. This is what those who gave us the instruments that are the raw material for psychological assessment have done.

Today, we are pleased to receive this new production, which is the result of patient, sustained work within the framework of scientific research, generously shared with the network by the author.

The possibility of having a national norm constructed with a valid methodology is a starting point for the continuation of research.

The epistemological framework, reference to previous studies, and the historical contextualization of the topic make this work a reference text that complements the previously cited works, strengthening the technique's foundation.

As we already know, graphic projective techniques have the virtue of providing access to deep aspects of personality with economy of time and resources. However, research on these techniques is often scarce compared to others. This is likely due to the interest in "objective" inventories and techniques, which require less interpretive skill from the evaluator and are intended to have less margin for error.

One more reason to welcome this volume!

Personally, I believe this book is the product not only of scientific work but also of the passion that Irene Sirianni puts into the task, a characteristic that represents her well. I thus open the door for readers to find useful tools with the same passion to be applied in the difficult but stimulating task of psychological assessment.

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Introduction

This research arises as a result of over twelve years of daily use of the test as an evaluator in the Argentine Republic, driven by the lack of national studies that include a representative sample of the entire population and the absence of validity and reliability scales.

It has been reviewed and corrected by juries as part of my doctoral thesis, which ensures that it is on the right path, both in the selection of the two thousand cases that make up the sample and, in the methodology, applied and the statistical tools used to reach the conclusions presented here.

This work addresses the validity and reliability of the application of the Person with a weapon test as a psychometric strategy for evaluating candidates who will assume the responsibility required by a service considered socially necessary for the comprehensive protection of people.

The selection processes of the different security forces and private security companies, although they have different guidelines and processes, require the implementation of a psychological evaluation for applicants. This allows for the identification of the main characteristics of their psychic structure, which must conform to healthy behavior patterns. Therefore, it is essential to focus on the validity and degree of reliability provided by the results of the psychometric properties.

This work develops an exploratory-descriptive research task, providing the first Argentine study on validity and reliability, making it possible to identify the validity and reliability characteristics of the Person with a weapon test in a large analyzed research sample.

To this end, we will address the main theoretical contributions generated so far regarding the use of projective tests as an evaluation strategy for candidates in the corresponding Armed Forces and Security Forces careers (henceforth referred to as the Armed Forces and Security Forces, or FF. AA. and FF. SS.) in Argentina.

Projective Techniques

Projective instruments have always been part of the mandatory debate in the field of psychodiagnostics, in all its areas. Professional practice in psychology is currently mediated by technology, and the immediacy of communication, which seems to be of great help in terms of the quantity of information but can also become an obstacle or severely diminish the quality of that information. Many professionals obtain material from the internet, which does not always meet the technical and scientific quality required by our profession, circulating publications within the mental health community that do not conform to scientific knowledge criteria and lack the minimum validity and reliability to be used as valid resources in psychodiagnostic evaluations.

It is the responsibility of psychologists to always keep in mind that our diagnosis, as professionals tasked with this, affects vital issues for other people. This requires our commitment to continuous training based on science and the permanent questioning of the validity and reliability of known instruments to adjust our practice to the ethical and legal standards regarding the proper use of psychological tests and evaluation techniques.

In the clinical area, our diagnosis will justify the choice of one treatment or another, a referral to psychiatric services, an admission or discharge in mental health or addiction services. Therefore, the consequences of an incorrect diagnosis necessarily lead to erroneous and iatrogenic treatment, which will permanently affect the mental health of the individuals involved.

Regarding educational psychology, any failure or error in diagnosis would have significant consequences for a child's or a developing subject's educational process, directly affecting their present and indirectly their future. For this reason, it is especially important to use reliable tools that ensure the safeguarding of the evaluated person's potential, or help them obtain the appropriate assistance if they present any issues that need to be addressed in that context.

In the workplace, a person may obtain a job position for which they lack the necessary emotional, interpersonal, or other competencies, or be deemed unfit for the position based on the required profile, be referred for a mental health leave, qualify and receive a promotion for a position they are psychologically unfit to assume, or lose the opportunity to take

a job for which they would be suitable, according to the psychodiagnostic assessment requested.

In legal and forensic matters, the expert opinion (which is why we are called upon by the judge as subject-matter experts) is a specialized diagnosis through which a person may obtain compensation for harm suffered, lose custody of their children, link minors to pathological individuals who do not offer them safety, lose their freedom, or be legally declared incapable of managing their own assets or making decisions regarding themselves, among other potential situational scenarios.

Although the expert opinion is not directly binding as evidence, it is a significant element that the justice system requests from us as experts and upon which it can base its decisions. In this branch of psychology, it becomes even more crucial to maintain scientific rigor when evaluating, diagnosing, and reporting what judicial authorities request regarding the evaluated subject.

As previously stated, the responsibility of the professional conducting the evaluations cannot be overlooked, as their diagnosis or specialized report will determine the decisions made by an organization, company, insurance company, etc.

On the Use of Tests in the Work evaluation

Within the branches of psychology, there is industrial psychology, which refers to a resource for understanding and explaining how cognitive processes, emotions, and behavioral aspects of individuals are influenced by social exchange (Allport, 1935 as cited in Morales et al., 2007) within the world of work (Arnold & Randall, 2012).

In its early stages, psychological evaluations were generally seen as diagnostic strategies assessing personality traits and their underlying structures, considered elements that generate certain behaviors. The arrival of the behavioral approach provided evaluation strategies that focused both on contextual analysis and on motivational aspects, pursuing specific goals. As a result, the measurement of behavior became central in the field of psychology (Aragón & Silva, 2002).

This discipline offers strategies for establishing specific profiles that candidates must possess to fill certain positions or provide specific services. In this context, general psychological evaluation, especially in the workplace, plays a crucial role by offering strategies that help identify certain skills in individuals to subsequently make accurate decisions (Negrón, 2004).

These psychological evaluation strategies help understand behaviors and predict a candidate's ability to adapt to a job position (whether a job role or the professional delivery of a service). These tools are called graphic projective tests and are used in both companies and institutions (Veccia et al., 2016; Filippi, 1995).

Binet and Spearman are recognized for initiating a new phase in the field of psychological tests. Over time, numerous types of tests have been developed to offer an objective, generally quantitative and comparative, appreciation of various aspects of behavior and personality, through methods that range from simple to complex (Chiriboga Sánchez, 2008).

Tests focus on defining psychological functions related to different aspects of personality. They are presented as an articulated set of problems, situations, or tasks that highlight these psychological functions (Fernández, 2009).

They also provide a unit of measurement that offers a set of indexes, such as scores, to facilitate the interpretation of results. Among the most common indexes are the validity coefficient, which indicates how well the function to be measured is appreciated, the reliability coefficient, which evaluates the consistency of scores over successive attempts, and the magnitude of measurement errors (Chiriboga Sánchez, 2008).

Both the drawing and the figure allow the psychologist to access specific data about the personality of the interviewee. Additionally, they can be categorized as expressive in the way they are administered, with a simple prompt requiring the interviewee to respond with a graphic image created by themselves (Celener, 2006).

According to Carmeño (2004), the advantages of graphic projective techniques are:

- a) The graphic language is not subject to conscious activity, allowing for the analysis of unconscious traits of personality and behavior.
- b) They are independent of the educational level attained by the interviewee.
- c) They are characterized by simplicity.
- d) They can be applied both individually and in groups.
- e) They can reveal both normal and pathological traits of personality and behavior.
- f) The prompts given are familiar and simple, making them motivating for the interviewee.
- g) However, this simplicity disguises important elements of behavior and personality that the subject is unaware of, allowing them to project their personality traits without external influence.

Therefore, projective tests are a category of psychological tests that present material in a way that the individual can organize, interpret, or elaborate, allowing them to project their psychological content. These tests are based on the idea that the responses given by the subject reveal aspects of their personality, emotions, thoughts, and internal experiences (De La Iglesia et al., 2013).

In addition to projective tests, there are other types of tests used in psychological evaluation. Questionnaires consist of direct questions (called items) on specific aspects, and the subject must choose between two or more alternatives to respond. Inventories, on the other hand, present an extensive list of aspects, and the subject indicates which ones they feel most identified with or connected to. Scales, in turn, are used to measure different attributes and are graded according to the subject's age.

This variety of instruments enriches the evaluator's possibilities, providing information about the evaluated subject through different means. According to the requirements of the evaluation, the professional will select those that are accessible to the subject being evaluated and that allow the gathering of data on the aspects for which the evaluation is requested, in educational, work, or judicial contexts, etc.

The conclusions that can be drawn will depend on the convergence and recurrence of the indicators found across the different instruments used in the selected evaluation battery. This implies that, according to good practice, a diagnostic conclusion should be reached through indicators from various tests, and it is strongly discouraged to base a diagnostic hypothesis on isolated techniques, an interview, or a single test, as the information obtained would be extremely poor, biased, and unsupported.

This is determined by evaluating the validity and reliability of these tests in sufficiently representative samples of the population, since not all existing projective techniques are scientifically valid for exploring what they intend to measure and for making well-founded conclusions or diagnoses.

Graphic projective techniques, like any psychological evaluation tool, offer scores or average values that are compared with those of the normal population concerning the psychological functions measured. Each experiment conducted with a psychological test establishes a relationship between two related facts, and to achieve this, control over certain variables is established, making them constants (Palacios García-Montes, 2011).

For execution, the objectives of the test are presented first, followed by a description of its structure. Information is also provided about the standardization process, general application instructions, and a detailed description of the test material, including instructions for each subtest (if applicable). Furthermore, instructions for evaluating the responses, statistical and psychometric information about the properties of the test, and tables with scores for different age groups, populations, and behaviors are included (Chiriboga Sánchez, 2008).

The goal of all these precautions is to establish a controlled situation within the possibilities offered by administering a test. A test must be a monitored tool, as being a scientific method, it requires accurate measurements and quantifiable resources. Measurement involves adopting numbers to describe aspects of a given phenomenon (Luna et al., 2015).

The use of scores is closely related to validity, reliability, and measurement error.

Therefore, it is essential to use an appropriate scale that relates to the measure.

In this sense, there are four main scales:

- The nominal scale, which uses numbers to designate categories or groups.
- The ordinal scale, where numbers are used to establish an order.
- The interval scale, in which equal numerical distances represent equal distances in the measured attribute or quality.
- The scale with a zero point, which allows all arithmetic operations and establishes the absolute magnitude of any measurable aspect.

Consequently, validity and reliability are two fundamental concepts in scientific research, especially in quantitative research. Both concepts focus on the quality of measurements and the consistency of the results obtained (Streiner & Norman, 2008).

Validity refers to the ability of the test to actually measure what it is intended to measure, while reliability is related to the consistency of the obtained measurements. The validity of a psychological test means that when a psychologist seeks to objectively and quantitatively assess a specific behavioral aspect, they must establish a measure to carry it out.

The psychologist defines the nature of what they want to measure and considers using a test as an evaluation instrument.

They then subject this test to a validation process, which involves establishing the validity coefficient of the test in relation to an external criterion, meaning evaluating how well the test actually measures what it is intended to measure (Chiriboga Sánchez, 2008).

Therefore, validity is linked to the accuracy or precision of a measurement or test. It indicates to what extent a data collection tool measures what it is intended to measure.

For example, if measuring people's intelligence, the validity of an intelligence test would be related to how well that test actually measures intelligence and no other factors or abilities.

There are different types of validity to consider in a study, such as content validity, which refers to how well the items or questions represent the construct to be measured; construct validity, which evaluates whether the tool accurately measures the underlying theoretical construct; and criterion validity, which compares the results of a tool with an established external criterion to determine if they are consistently related (Hinkin, 1998).

On the other hand, reliability refers to the consistency and stability of the results obtained through a data collection tool.

Reliability can be assessed using different methods, such as the reliability coefficient (e.g., Cronbach's alpha), which indicates how consistent the responses are across the items of a scale (Hair et al., 2019).

In this way, a measurement scale is considered reliable when, when applied to equal magnitudes, it provides consistent measurements.

To determine the reliability of a test, the correlation coefficient between the scores obtained by the same subjects in the first and second application of the test is calculated, usually within a time frame that does not exceed one week, depending on the test in question. It is important to mention that every measurement process has an error margin, known as measurement error. Measurement errors can be constant or casual and must be considered when interpreting the results of a test (Chiriboga Sánchez, 2008).

According to Didier Anzieu (1961) in his book *Los métodos proyectivos* (The Projective Methods), reliability in these techniques refers to the "agreement between judges" or inter-judge reliability, meaning that different judges examining the same material will or will not reach the same conclusions. This depends on the judges' competence and experience.

As for the validity of projective instruments, according to Anzieu, it is linked to the scientific process of hypothesis validation. The formulation and confirmation or refutation of hypotheses are closely related to the interpretation method used and, therefore, to the theoretical foundations and conceptual framework.

Validity is linked to the ability of these techniques to provide accurate and relevant information in the context of their application and to support conclusions based on the underlying theoretical model (Sneiderman, 2011).

Regarding inter-judge validity as a methodological strategy, Cabero & Loscertales (1996) argue that to ensure the reliability of a categorical system, expert consultation is essential, and the degree of agreement in interpreting this system should be measured.

The analysis of matches and discrepancies is the basis of the inter-judge agreement methodology (Muñoz et al., 2006), but the aim is to minimize the inevitable personal bias by providing clear and stable criteria.

Maintaining a high level of rigor in these criteria is essential, especially when there are more judges.

Once the criteria are established, the limits of acceptability for agreements must be defined. However, as Umesh et al. (1989) assert, deciding whether a particular percentage of agreement is sufficient or insufficient is not an easy task in practice.

Consequently, interpreting the results of projective techniques should not be an isolated, subjective task, but rather communicable and explanatory, allowing for the steps leading to specific conclusions to be described (Sneiderman, 2011).

In this context, the different levels addressed to describe the process leading to hypotheses and interpretations in projective techniques are relevant. Inter-judge reliability and the search for consensus are essential approaches applied in evaluating results (Sneiderman, 2011).

This work will analyze the validity and reliability of the application of the graphic projective technique, the Person with a weapon test (TPA), created in Peru by Lic. Morocho Vázquez (2002), which arises from an adaptation of the Human Figure Drawing (HFD) test initially proposed by Florence L. Goodenough.

Analysis of Inter-Judge Validity – Pearson's R

Characteristics of Pearson's R (Pearson Correlation Coefficient)

It is used to measure the linear relationship between two quantitative variables.

Range of values: From -1 to +1.

- $r = +1$ → Perfect positive correlation (when one variable increases, the other also increases proportionally).
- $r = -1$ → Perfect negative correlation (when one variable increases, the other decreases proportionally).
- $r = 0$ → No linear correlation between the variables.

Direction of the relationship:

- Positive: As X increases, Y increases.
- Negative: As X increases, Y decreases.

Strength of the correlation:

- 0.00 - 0.30 → Weak correlation.
- 0.30 - 0.60 → Moderate correlation.
- 0.60 - 0.90 → Strong correlation.
- 0.90 - 1.00 → Very strong correlation.

Inter-Judge Validity

The results of the global relative agreement analysis using Pearson's correlation coefficient show a high and consistent agreement among the three judges who evaluated the same protocols.

The correlations are exceptionally close to 1, suggesting a very high level of agreement in their evaluations.

- Location: The correlation of 0.999188 indicates almost perfect agreement in the evaluation of the location of elements in the drawings.
- Size and layout: The correlation of 0.999167 also indicates almost perfect agreement in evaluating the size and layout of the drawings.
- Shading: The correlation of 1 indicates complete agreement in the evaluation of shading.
- Gaze, posture, history, integration, type, and action: The correlations of 1 for all of these variables indicate total agreement among the judges in evaluating these aspects.
- Score: The correlation of 0.999969 indicates almost perfect agreement in assigning scores to the graphic indicators.

- Range: The correlation of 1 indicates total agreement in evaluating the ranges.

In summary, the results show an extremely high agreement among the three judges in evaluating all the variables.

This consistency suggests a reliable and robust interpretation of the evaluated protocols. The high correlation across all variables indicates that the three judges arrived at very similar and consistent evaluations in terms of the structure, expression, and symbolic meaning of the drawings.

The high degree of agreement suggests that the evaluations made by the three judges are highly reliable and consistent regarding these specific scores.

The correlation close to 1 in most categories indicates that all judges reached virtually identical evaluations.

Results of the variables.

Variables	Pearson's R
Location	0,999188
Size	0,999167
Drawing	0,999167
Shading	1
Gaze	1
Posture	1
Story	1
Integration	1
Type	1
Action	1
Score	0,999969
Range	1

Reliable Interpretation of Protocols

The consistency in the evaluations of the protocols indicates that the results are reliable and that the interpretations derived from them are solid.

This is essential in the context of personnel selection for security positions, where a precise assessment of the candidates' aptitudes and suitability is required.

Therefore, it is observed that carrying out a reliable interpretation of the protocols used in the evaluation of candidates for security positions is of utmost importance.

Moreover, reliability in evaluation significantly minimizes the risks associated with selecting unsuitable candidates.

The safety of the community and the security employees themselves heavily depends on the quality of the selection.

An error in the evaluation could expose the community to dangerous situations or result in the improper use of force by employees.

Conclusion

This paper has explored the validity and reliability of the Person with a weapon test as a projective and psychometric tool in evaluating candidates for roles that require carrying weapons.

Throughout this research, the importance of precise and specific methods to assess the competencies and psychological characteristics necessary to perform these high-responsibility roles has been emphasized.

The Person with a weapon test has proven to be a simple and effective technique for revealing crucial aspects of the candidates' personalities.

The ability of this technique to identify traits of adaptation and emotional maladjustment, as well as its ease of application and evaluation, make it a valuable tool for psychodiagnostic professionals in various fields.

The results suggest that integrating the test into the selection processes can significantly improve the identification of suitable candidates, thus promoting safety and efficiency within the Armed Forces and Security Forces, as well as among members of private security companies.

Furthermore, the detailed analysis of candidates' graphic and narrative expression provides deep insights into their capabilities and limitations, allowing for a more comprehensive and accurate evaluation.

In conclusion, the implementation of the The Person with a weapon test as part of the selection process for roles involving the use of weapons presents an effective and reliable strategy.

The validation of its effectiveness and reliability in this study supports its continued use and its potential to contribute to a more rigorous and appropriate personnel selection, ensuring that only the most prepared and psychologically fit individuals assume these important roles of protection and security.

Considering that in Argentina, most graphic tests do not have validity and reliability established through scientific methodology, and in some cases, lack updated psychometric property analysis for our population, the use of this test is recommended in other areas, such as educational, clinical, forensic, or legal psychodiagnostics, and evaluations for driver's licenses.

As seen in previous chapters, the test provides substantial and complex information about variables to explore in different fields, not only in occupational psychology.

In addition to being a novel, cost-effective, quick, and simple technique, it provides information about the internal world of the evaluated individual that cannot be obtained through other commonly used graphic techniques, expanding its use to evaluations of all kinds.

Another significant advantage of the The Person with a weapon test is that it does not require a high level of education to understand the requirements it poses.

While the sample used consists of individuals with complete secondary education, it could be used with individuals who have incomplete secondary education or completed primary education, provided they understand simple instructions.

The test explores variables such as inhibition, attention, aggression, impulsivity, adjustment to norms, use of authority over others, self-harm potential, etc., which we could not easily access through other graphic tests and can help us establish, through recurrence and convergence with other tests, scientifically accurate diagnoses.

The fact that this test has achieved such solid inter-rater validity positions it as a highly reliable tool for colleagues who require results based on scientific practices in different areas of psychodiagnostics.

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